

PREVALENCE OF NEONATAL SEPSIS AMONG NEWBORNS UNIT AND ANTIMICROBIALS IS USED IN HOSPITALS GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE IN SANA'A, YEMEN

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Article Received on 05 Jan. 2026,
Article Revised on 25 Jan. 2026,
Article Published on 01 Feb. 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18478747>

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How to cite this Article: Abdualdaim Mohammed Mukred* (2026). Prevalence of Neonatal Sepsis Among Newborns Unit and Antimicrobials is Used in Hospitals Government and Private in Sana'a, Yemen. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(2), 596-612.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Nearly 3 million newborns suffer from sepsis globally each year and sepsis is considered one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality in neonates, despite recent advances in health care units. The main burden of the problem falls on the developing world. **Objective:** The current study aimed to evaluate the prevalence of Neonatal sepsis among newborns unit and antimicrobials is used in government and private hospitals in Sana'a, Yemen. **Methods:** The current study aimed to evaluate the prevalence of Neonatal sepsis among newborns unit and antimicrobials is used in government and private hospitals in Sana'a, Yemen. A cross-sectional study was conducted on (200) children suspected of having neonatal sepsis from both hospitals (100government, 100 private) in the period from (1January, 2024 until 30April, 2024). Medical information on the newborns was collected using a structured

questionnaire. The sample has been examined of members to confirm the growth of the pathogen, its type, and the degree sensitivity and resistance to the antibiotics that were used during treatment. Data were collected and analysed using (SPSS.V25) program and tested using Chi square to verify the extent of relationships between variables within the study at the significance level ($P < 0.005$). **Results:** The results showed that the prevalence of neonatal sepsis was 107 (53%), the EOS was higher 74(69.2%) than LOS 33(30.8%), and there is a significant effect ($p = 0.047$) of the prevalence of the neonatal sepsis in government hospitals (56.1%) higher than in private hospitals. Most of the pathogens were of the GP bacteria

(50.5%), the most common bacteria were (*Staph.spp*), (49.5%) followed by (*Pseudomonas.aeruginosa*, *E. coli* and *Klebsiella.spp*) bacteria, respectively (15.9%, 10.3%, 9.3%). Most patients with EOS has the highest infection with GN bacteria (55.4), while LOS has the highest infection with GP with statistically significant differences ($p<0.05$), the prevalence of GP bacteria in hospitals Government (65.96%) higher than private hospitals, with statistically significant differences ($p<0.05$). The highest bacterial resistance was to (Amoxicillin) at a rate of (100%), followed by (Cefuroxime, piperacillin and Ceftriaxone) with rates respectively (98.7%, 92.8%, 90%), while bacterial resistance was moderate to the both drugs (Cefazidime and Cefepime) with rates respectively (63,.6%,66%), and the least bacterial resistance to the drug (Meropenem) was 1 (1%). There was a statistically significant effect ($p<0.05$) of bacterial resistance (GN–GP) to both drugs (Gentamycin, Piperacillin, amoxicillin, Augmentin and Cefepime). **Conclusion:** The prevalence of Neonatal sepsis in government hospitals was higher than in private hospitals, which indicates the need to improve the health situation in government health facilities, and researchers recommend conducting more studies and using broader samples of the groups most exposed to the disease and studying Antibiotic-resistant bacterial pathogen.

KEYWORDS: Neonatal sepsis; Etiology of the Neonatal sepsis; Resistance to antibiotics.

INTRODUCTION

Nearly 3 million newborns suffer from sepsis worldwide each year.^[1] Sepsis is considered one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality in neonates, despite recent developments in health care units. The main burden of the problem is in the developing world while most of the evidence is derived from developed countries.^[2]

Sepsis is a systemic inflammatory reaction caused by microorganisms (bacteria, viruses, or fungi) that invade the bloodstream, resulting in severe symptoms such as fever and shock^[3] Neonatal sepsis is further classified into early neonatal sepsis (EOS) if the clinical feature of sepsis occurs within the first week of life and late neonatal sepsis (LOS) if it occurs between 7 - 28 days of life.^[4,5] Early detection of neonatal sepsis is difficult, so antibiotics are given empirically when sepsis is suspected to prevent serious consequences.

Antibiotics are among the most used medications in the neonatal intensive care units (NICU).^[6] Almost all neonates in an NICU receive antibiotics during their hospitalization, but only 5% have a positive blood culture. Most of the antibiotic courses are given

empirically before 72 h of life, and 60% of these courses are prolonged for more than 48–72 h despite negative blood culture and a stable clinical condition.^[7] Patel et al. found that 35% of neonates receive at least one inappropriate course of antibiotics during their NICU stay.^[8] Unnecessary use of broad-spectrum antibiotics in empirical therapy increases multidrug-resistant microorganisms in neonatal intensive care units (NICU) and places a significant burden on developing countries. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines antibiotic resistance as a major public health problem that requires immediate attention.^[9]

Neonatal sepsis in neonates are 3 to 20 times higher in developing countries, and in some countries, nearly half of patients in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) become infected.

Mortality rates from neonatal sepsis may be as high as 52%, contributing to approximately 1 million deaths, and is responsible for approximately 30-50% of all neonatal deaths in developing countries, although sepsis-related deaths are largely preventable.^[10,11] However, neonatal mortality and the frequency of sepsis vary among the population from one country to another. In epidemiological data reports, 99% of neonatal deaths occurred in low- and middle-income countries and 1% in high-income countries.^[12]

Although high burden of neonatal sepsis related mortality and mortality are being reported from developing countries, most scientific evidences are derived from developed countries. Yemen is suffering from an ongoing war that began in 2015. The war has devastated the health system, leaving health facilities either non-functional or partially functioning.^[13]

This in turn exacerbated the recklessness of the community's health situation and the spread and outbreak of many diseases, especially among children throughout the Republic. A study conducted at the (Maternity and Childhood Hospital in the city of Mukalla) indicated that the high mortality rate in newborns reached (22.6%), with (35%) of the deaths resulting from neonatal infection.^[14]

In another study conducted by Adeeb et al in the city of Sana'a, this study showed that among 199 newborns suspected of having neonatal sepsis, 154 (77.38%) had culture-confirmed sepsis. Early neonatal sepsis (EOS) was higher (50.25%) than late neonatal sepsis (LOS) (27.13%).^[15]

Given the high prevalence of sepsis and mortality in preterm infants and its long-term consequences on growth and development, efforts to reduce infection rates in this vulnerable

population are one of the most important interventions in neonatal care especially in developing countries.^[16]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design : A cross-sectional study was designed from (1 January, 2024 to 30 April, 2024) to evaluate the prevalence of Neonatal sepsis among newborns unit and antimicrobials is used in government and private hospitals in Sana'a, Yemen. This design allows data to be collected at a specific time, providing a quick overview of the extent of the disease's prevalence among the children of the target population (Newborns of Sana'a city).

Study population: All new-borns status from 1 day into 3 months of admission to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) in hospitals on suspicion of sepsis. New-borns with clinical signs and symptoms indicating septicaemia were considered eligible for the study.

Exclusion criteria: Exclude new-borns with incomplete data or those transferred from other facilities without adequate prior medical records.

Data collection: The all of data collection from government and private hospitals in Sana'a, through medical records and laboratory reports, these data provided additional information on the prevalence of neonatal sepsis (septicaemia in new-borns) at hospitals, in addition to any existing treatment and management practices that were conducted on the target sample.

Sample volume: The sample of the current study consisted of (200) new-borns suspected of having neonatal sepsis (septicaemia in newborns) at hospitals (government and private) and the necessary medical tests were performed to detect infection (Neonatal sepsis).

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 25. Differences between groups were tested for significance through the Chi-square test. The data was expressed as a percentage. Values of $P < 0.05$ are considered statistically significant values. Correlations are also considered significant at the significance level ($P < 0.05$).

Results: Total of (200) newborns suspected of having neonatal sepsis. The neonatal sepsis was distributed according to gender (males – females). The number of males 121 (60.5%) in the neonatal sepsis was higher than the number of females 79 (39.5%) as the Figure (4). And it was also distributed according to age into three age groups: It was found that the age group

(<1month) represented the highest percentage 140 (70%) and followed by the age group (1 – 2 month) at a rate of 45 (22.5%) and (2 – 3month) at a rate of 15 (7.5%) as the Table (1) and It was also shown that the sample was distributed equally according to hospitals (government - private) in the neonatal sepsis at a rate of 100 (50%) as the figure (2).

Table 1: General distribution of demographic variables (gender – age groups – hospitals).

Variables		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	121	60.5
	Female	79	39.5
	Total	200	100
Age groups	<1 month	140	70
	(1 – 2)month	45	22.5
	(2 – 3)month	15	7.5
	Total	200	100
Hospitals	Governmental	100	50
	Private	100	50
	Total	200	100

Data represented as frequency and percent%

Figure 1: The general distribution of the gender variable (males - females) in the neonatal sepsis.

Figure 2; The general distribution of hospitals (government - private) in the neonatal sepsis.

In these study out of 200 newborns, is found 107 (53%) positive cases for bacterial isolates growth, as the figure (4.1.2.1), The bacterial isolates was distributed according to name of bacteria, the most common bacterial isolates in the Neonatal sepsis was (*Staph.spp*) at a rate of (49.5%), followed by (*Pseudomonas.aeruginosa*, *E.coli* And *Klebsiella.spp*) were distributed respectively (15.9%,10.3%,9.3%), while non-common bacterial isolates as(*Raoultella.ornithinolytica*, *Micrococcus.spp*, *Citrobacter*, *Enterococcus*, *Burkholderia.spp*, *Kocuria.variants*, *Serratia. marcescens*, *Pandoraea.spp*, *Leuconostoe.mesenteroides*, *Streptococcus.spp*) respectively (0.9%, 0.9%, 3.7%,2.8%, 1.9%, 0.9%, 0.9%, 0.9%, 0.9%, 0.9%) as the figure (3), The table (2) show the Prevalence of the neonatal sepsis as follows:

Table 2: The prevalence of growth bacterial isolates (Neonatal sepsis) among newborns unit in hospitals Government and private in Sana'a, Yemen.

Variables		Frequency	Percent
growth of bacterial isolates			
	Growth	107	54
	non-growth	93	46
	Total	200	100
The name of bacteria isolates			
	<i>E.coli</i>	11	10.3
	<i>Pseudomonas.aeruginosa</i>	17	15.9
	<i>Staph.spp</i>	53	49.5
	<i>Serratia . marcescens</i>	3	2.8
	<i>Klebsiella.spp</i>	10	9.3

<i>Raoultella.ornithinolytica</i>	1	0.9
<i>Micrococcus.spp</i>	1	0.9
<i>Citrobacter</i>	4	3.7
<i>Enterococcus</i>	2	1.9
<i>Burkholderia.spp</i>	1	0.9
<i>Kocuria.variants</i>	1	0.9
<i>Pandoraea.spp</i>	1	0.9
<i>Leuconostoe.mesenteroides</i>	1	0.9
<i>Streptococcus.spp</i>	1	0.9
Total	107	100

Data represented as frequency and percent%.

The name of bacteria isolates

Figure 3: Distribution of bacterial isolates (Gram positive - Gram negative) causing the disease.

Table 3: The relationship between prevalence of growth of bacterial isolates and demographic variables (gender - age groups - Hospitals).

Variables		growth of bacterial isolates		Total	P value
		Growth	non-growth		
		NO.(%)	NO.(%)	NO.(%)	
Gender					
	Male	67 (62.6)	54(58.7)	121(60.5)	0.63
	Female	40(37.4)	38(41.3)	79(39.5)	
	Total	107(100)	93(100)	200(100)	

Age groups					
	<1 month	74(69.2)	66(71.7)	140(7)	0.289
	(1 - 2)month	27(25.2)	17(18.5)	45(22.5)	
	(2 - 3)month	6(5.6)	9(9.8)	15(7.5)	
	Total	107(100)	93(100)	200(100)	
Hospitals					
	Governmental	60(56.1)	39(42.4)	100(50)	0.047*
	Private	47(43.9)	53(57.6)	100(50)	
	Total	107(100)	93(100)	200(100)	

*P value was significant at <0.05 and calculated for chi square test.

Table (3) show that most of those infected with the neonatal sepsis are males (62.6%), while infected with female at a rate of (37.4%) and most of them are in the age group (<1month) with a percentage of 74 (69.2%), followed by both age groups (1 – 2 months) at a rate of 27 (25.2%) and (2 – 3 month) at a rate of (5.6%) most of prevalence of neonatal sepsis in government hospitals (56.1%), while prevalence of neonatal sepsis in private hospitals (43.9%) There is a significant effect ($p=0.047^*$) of prevalence rate in government hospitals being higher than private hospitals.

Table 4: The relationship between the type of bacterial isolates (GN – GP) in Neonatal sepsis and variables (gender – classification of Neonatal sepsis – hospitals).

Variables		the type of bacteria isolates		Total NO.(%)	P value
		Positive NO.(%)	Negative NO.(%)		
The Gender of patient					0.128
	Male	30 (44.7)	37 (55.3)	67 (62.6)	
	Female	24 (60)	16(40)	40(37.4)	
	Total	54(100)	53(100)	107(100)	
classification of Neonatal sepsis					0.027*
	(EOS)	33(44.6)	41(55.4)	74(69.2)	
	(LOS)	21(63.6)	12(36.4)	33(30.8)	
	Total	54(50.5)	53(49.5)	107(100)	
The hospitals					0.003*
	Governmental	38(63.3)	22(36.6)	60(56.1)	
	Private	16(34.04)	31(65.96)	47(43.9)	
	Total	54(50.5)	53(49.5)	107(100)	

*P value was significant at <0.05 and calculated for chi square test.

Table (4) show that infection with GP bacteria (50.5%) is higher than infection with GN bacteria (49.5%). most males are infected with GN bacteria at a rate of (55.3%), while infected with GP bacteria at a rate of (44.7%), and the most females are infected by GP bacteria at a rate of (60%), while infected with GN bacteria at a rate of (30%). EOS have the

highest infection with GN at a rate of (55.4%) while infected with GP bacteria at a rate of (44.6%), and LOS the highest infection of GP (63.6%) while infected with GN bacteria at a rate of (36.4%) with statistically significant differences ($p < 0.005$), and the prevalence of GP bacteria in government hospitals (63.3%) while prevalence GN bacteria at a rate of (36.6%), and prevalence of GN bacteria in private hospitals (65.96%) while prevalence GP bacteria at a rate of (34.04%) with There are statistically significant differences ($p < 0.005$).

Table 5: Distribution of bacterial isolates According to classification of Neonatal sepsis (EOS- LOS).

Variables	Total	classification of Neonatal sepsis	
		(EOS)	(LOS)
		NO.(%)	NO.(%)
The name of bacteria			
<i>E.coli</i>	11(10.3)	9(12.2)	2(7.4)
<i>Pseudomonas.aeruginosa</i>	17(15.9)	12(16.2)	5(18.5)
<i>Staph.spp</i>	53(49.5)	33(44.6)	20(60.6)
<i>Serratia . marcescens</i>	3(2.8)	3(4.1)	0(0.0)
<i>Klebsiella.spp</i>	10(9.3)	7(9.5)	3(9.10)
<i>Raoultella.ornithinolytica</i>	1(0.9)	1(1.4)	0(0.0)
<i>Micrococcus.spp</i>	1(0.9)	0(0.0)	1(3)
<i>Citrobacter</i>	4(3.7)	4(5.4)	0(0.0)
<i>Enterococcus</i>	2(1.9)	2(2.7)	0(0.0)
<i>Burkholderia.spp</i>	1(0.9)	1(1.4)	0(0.0)
<i>Kocuria.variants</i>	1(0.9)	1(1.4)	0(0.0)
<i>Pandora.a.spp</i>	1(0.9)	1(1.4)	0(0.0)
<i>Leuconostoe.mesenteroides</i>	1(0.9)	0(0.0)	1(3)
<i>Streptococcus.spp</i>	1(0.9)	0(0.0)	1(3)
Total	107(100)	74(69.2)	33(30.8)

Data represented as frequency and percent%.

Table (5) show that the prevalence of EOS was (69. 2%), while LOS was 33 (30.8%) Most of the pathogens bacteria in EOS with (*Staph.spp*) at a rate of (44.6%), followed by (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *E.coli*), with a rate of (16.2, 12.2%) followed by both (*Micrococcus.spp*, *Serratia. marcescens*, *Citrobacter*, *Enterococcus*, *Burkholderia.spp*, *Kocuria.variants*, *Pandora.a.spp*, *Raoultella.ornithinolytica*) respectively (5.4%, 4.1%, 2.7%, 1.4%,1.4%, 1.4%) it is found in EOS only. while Most of the pathogens bacteria in LOS with (*Staph.spp*) at a rate of (60.6%) followed by (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Klebsiella.spp*), with a rate of (18.5%, 9.10%) followed by both (*Leuconostoe. mesenteroides*, *Streptococcus.spp*, *Micrococcus.spp*) respectively (3%)it is found in LOS only.

Distribution of bacterial isolates According to classification of Neonatal sepsis (EOS- LOS)

Figure 4: Distribution of bacterial isolates According to classification of Neonatal sepsis (EOS- LOS).

Table 6: Overall status of antibiotic resistance against type bacterial isolates (Gram negative - Gram positive).

Variables	the type of bacteria		Total	P value
	Positive	Negative		
	NO.(%)	NO.(%)	NO.(%)	
Antibiotic resistant				
Meropenem	0(0.0)	1(100)	1(1.0)	0.3
Imipenem	0(0.0)	1(100)	1(3.3)	0.611
Gentamycin	0(0.0)	2(100)	2(3.4)	0.000*
Ceftazidime	21(42.9)	28(57.1)	49(63.6)	0.619
Cefepime	26(41.9)	36(58.1)	62(66)	0.000*
Piperacillin	46(51.1)	44(48.9)	90(92.8)	0.000*
Linezolid	2(100)	0(0.0)	2(3.8)	0.835
Vancomycin	5(100)	0(0.0)	5(8.2)	0.536
Trimethoprim	18(48.6)	19(51.4)	37(57.8)	0.998
Cefotaxim	44(63.8)	25(36.2)	69(92)	0.142
Augmentin	14(35)	26(65)	40(85.1)	0.045*
Amoxicillin	49(77.8)	14(22.2)	63(100)	0.000*
Cefuroxime	44(59.5)	30(40.5)	74(98.7)	0.411
Ceftriaxone	14(38.9)	22(61.1)	36(90)	0.166
Erythromycin	0(0.0)	2(66.7)	2(50)	0.248

*P value was significant at <0.05 and calculated for chi square test.

Table (6) show that resistance to GN bacteria is higher for each of drug (Gentamycin, Meropenem, Imipenem, Erythromycin, Augmentin, Ceftriaxone, Cefepime Cefazidime, and Trimethoprim) respectively (100%, 100%,100%, 66.7%, 65%,61.1%, 58.1%,51.4%), while resistance to GP bacteria was higher for each of drug (Linezolid, Vancomycin, Piperacillin, Cefotaxim, Cefuroxime and Amoxicillin) respectively (100%,100%, 77.8%, 63.8%, 59.5%, 57.1%, 51.1%), that there was a statistically significant effect ($p < 0.05$) for bacterial resistance (GP – GN) for both drugs (Gentamycin, Piperacillin, amoxicillin, Augmentin and Cefepime).

Table 7: Antibiotic resistance levels of bacteria isolated from neonatal sepsis hospitals in Sana'a city, Yemen.

Variables	Amoxicillin	Piperacillin	Amikacin	Augmentin	Imipenem
	NO.(%)	NO.(%)	NO.(%)	NO.(%)	NO.(%)
<i>E.coli</i>	9(100)	10(90.9)	-	10(100)	0(0.0)
<i>Ps. Aeruginosa</i>	1(100)	14(87.5)	0(0.0)	2(100)	0(0.0)
<i>Staph.spp</i>	48(100)	47(97.9)	0(0.0)	11(64.7)	0(0.0)
<i>Serratia . marcescens</i>	-	3(100)	0(0.0)	2(100)	0(0.0)
<i>Klebsiella.spp</i>	-	9(100)	1(33.3)	6(85.7)	1(14.3)
<i>Raoultella.ornithinolytica</i>	-	1(100)	0(0.0)	1(100)	0(0.0)
<i>Micrococcus.spp</i>	1(100)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(100)	0(0.0)
<i>Citrobacter</i>	-	3(75)	-	4(100)	0(0.0)
<i>Enterococcus</i>	2(100)	-	0(0.0)	-	-
<i>Burkholderia.spp</i>	-	0(0.0)	1(100)	1(100)	-
<i>Kocuria.variants</i>	1(100)	1(100)	-	1(100)	-
<i>Pandoraea.spp</i>	-	1(100)	1(100)	-	0(0.0)
<i>Leuconostoe.mesenteroides</i>	1(100)	1(100)	-	1(100)	-
<i>Streptococcus.spp</i>	-	-	-	40(85.1)	-
Total	63(100)	90(92.8)	3(6.5)	40(85.1)	1(3.3)
Variables	Meropenem	Ceftazidime	Cefepime	Cefuroxime	Ceftriaxone
<i>E.coli</i>	0(0.0)	2(20)	4(80)	10(100)	10(100)
<i>Pseudomonas.aeruginosa</i>	0(0.0)	14(82.4)	16(94.1)	43(97.7)	1(100)
<i>Staph.spp</i>	0(0.0)	20(69)	26(53.1)	3(100)	15(83.3)
<i>Serratia . marcescens</i>	0(0.0)	1(50)	2(100)	-	2(100)
<i>Klebsiella.spp</i>	1(10)	7(77.8)	7(77.8)	8(100)	1(100)
<i>Raoultella.ornithinolytica</i>	0(0.0)	1(100)	1(100)	1(100)	1(100)
<i>Micrococcus.spp</i>	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(100)	-
<i>Citrobacter</i>	0(0.0)	2(50)	3(75)	3(100)	4(100)
<i>Enterococcus</i>	-	-	2(100)	2(100)	2(100)
<i>Burkholderia.spp</i>	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	-	0(0.0)
<i>Kocuria.variants</i>	0(0.0)	1(100)	0(0.0)	1(100)	-
<i>Pandoraea.spp</i>	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(100)	-
<i>Leuconostoe.mesenteroides</i>	0(0.0)	1(100)	1(100)	1(100)	-
<i>Streptococcus.spp</i>	0(0.0)	-	-	-	-
Total	1(1)	49(63.6)	62(66)	74(98.7)	36(90)
Variables	Vancomycin	Erythromycin	Gentamycin	Linezolid	Trimethoprim

<i>E.coli</i>	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	-	8(72.7)
<i>Pseudomonas.aeruginosa</i>	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(33.3)	2(4.3)	1(50)
<i>Staph.spp</i>	4(8.3)	-	0(0.0)	-	18(60)
<i>Serratia . marcescens</i>	-	-	-	-	1(33.3)
<i>Klebsiella.spp</i>	0(0.0)	-	0(0.0)	-	4(57.1)
<i>Raoultella.ornithinolytica</i>	-	-	0(0.0)	-	0(0.0)
<i>Micrococcus.spp</i>	0(0.0)	-	-	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
<i>Citrobacter</i>	-	-	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	2(50)
<i>Enterococcus</i>	0(0.0)	2(100.0)	-	-	2(100)
<i>Burkholderia.spp</i>	-	-	1(100)	-	0(0.0)
<i>Kocuria.variants</i>	0(0.0)	-	-	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
<i>Pandoraea.spp</i>	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Leuconostoe.mesenteroides</i>	1(100)	-	-	0(0.0)	1(100)
<i>Streptococcus.spp</i>	0(0.0)	-	-	-	-
Total	5(8.2)	2(50)	2(3.4)	2(3.8)	37(57.8)

Data represented as frequency and percent%.

Table (7) show that the bacterial resistance was moderate to the both drugs (Cefazidime and Cefepime) with rates respectively (63.6%, 66%) and followed by to both drug (Trimethoprim and Erythromycin) with rates respectively (57.8%, 50%).the least bacterial isolates resistance for each of drug (Vancomycin, Gentamycin, Linezolid, Imipenem and Meropenem) with rates respectively (8.2%, 3.4%, 3.8%, 3.3%, 1%). It was found that the most resistant bacteria were (*Staph.spp*) followed by (*Pseudomonas.aeruginosa*) and (*E. coli*).

DISCUSSION

Globally, sepsis remains a major cause of morbidity and mortality in neonates, despite recent advances in healthcare units. The main burden of the problem is in the developing world while most of the evidence is derived from developed countries.^[1]

In our current study, among 200 (100%) newborns suspected of having sepsis, the prevalence of neonatal sepsis was 107(53%) positive cases of bacterial growth. The EOS was higher 74(69.2%) than LOS 33(30.8%). This is lower than what was found in the study^[15] conducted in Sana'a. The prevalence of neonatal sepsis was 154 (77.38%) who had culture-proven sepsis. Early neonatal sepsis (EOS) was higher (50.25%; 100/199) than late neonatal sepsis (LOS) (27.13%; 54/199).

In another study by.^[17] In Ethiopia, the overall prevalence of neonatal sepsis was 77.9%. Of this, 65% and %35 of neonates developed early neonatal sepsis and late neonatal sepsis, respectively.

In our current study, infection with GP bacteria (50.5%) was higher than infection with GN bacteria (49.5%), and the most common types of pathogens were (*Staph.spp*) with a rate of (49.5%), followed by bacteria (*Pseudomonas.aeruginosa*, *E. coli* and *Klebsiella.spp*) which amounted, respectively, to (15.9%,10.3% and 9.3%). Most of the causes of sepsis were bacteria (*Staph.spp*) with a percentage of 53 (49.5%), with (44.5%)causing early neonatal sepsis with this type of bacteria, followed by bacteria (*Pseudomonas.aeruginosa*) with a percentage of (16.2%) and bacteria (*E. coli*) with a percentage (12.2%). This result was consistent with the study^[18] among these isolates, 378 isolates (55.67%) were GP bacteria, and 301 isolates (44.33%) were GN bacteria. The most frequently isolated pathogens were coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS) (36.52%), followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (20.47%) and *Escherichia coli* (13.84%). In EOS 121, strains were found, representing. CoNS the majority (33.88%), followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (23.97%) and *Escherichia coli* (8.26%).

Where the most common pathogens isolated from blood were coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS), which were represented by two dominant species: *S. epidermidis* and *S. haemolyticus*, Next *Klebsiella spp.* Strains and *E. coli*, which is mostly found in cases of EO-BSI. No single strain of *S. agalactiae* (GBS) has been isolated and a study.^[15] The majority of isolated bacteria (74.39%) were GN *Burkholderia cepacia* (39%) and *Klebsiella oxytoca* (13%) is the most common pathogen of EOS and LOS. The most common Grampositive pathogens were *Staphylococcus haemolyticus* (9.1%) and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (7.1%).

The infant may acquire the pathogen either in utero or during birth^[19] Hospitals is also one of the risk factors contributing to the spread of neonatal sepsis, especially with the lack of proper supervision. Risk factors include the use of central venous catheters and other invasive medical devices, in addition to treatment in hospital for long periods.^[20]

Most males are infected with GN bacteria at a rate of (69.8%), while most females are infected with GP bacteria at a rate of (44.4%). It turns out that those with early sepsis (EOS) have the highest infection with GN bacteria (GN) at a rate of (55.4%)While late sepsis (EOS) the highest infection with GP bacteria (GP) (63.6%)with statistically significant differences ($p<0.005$) and it turns out that the prevalence of GP bacteria in government hospitals (63.3%) is higher than in Special hospitals, with statistically significant differences ($p<0.005$) This result is consistent with the study.^[21] Of a total of 586 patients, 398 (67.9%) were male. In

another study the prevalence of neonatal sepsis was 20 (71.4%) males and 8 (28.6%) females, indicating a male predominance.^[22]

Neonatal sepsis is managed according to WHO guidelines that recommend ampicillin and cloxacillin Gentamicin as first-line antibiotics.^[23]

In our current study, treatment was limited to the use of several groups of antibiotics, such as Amino-penicillin, Cephalosporin, and Aminoglycosides. The highest bacterial resistance was to (Amoxicillin) (100%) followed by (Cefuroxime, piperacillin and Ceftriaxone) respectively (98.7%,92.8%, 90%), while bacterial resistance was moderate to the both drugs (Cefazidime and Cefepime) respectively (63.6%,66%), and the least bacterial resistance to the drug (Meropenem) With a rate of 1 (1%). Resistance to GN bacteria was higher for both (Gentamycin, Augmentin and Cefepime) respectively (100%, 65%, 58.1%), while resistance to GP bacteria was higher for both (Piperacillin and Amoxicillin) respectively (77.8 %, 51.1%). There was a statistically significant effect ($p < 0.05$) for resistance.

Bacterial (Gram positive - Gram negative) for both drugs (Gentamycin, Piperacillin, amoxicillin, Augmentin and Cefepime) in a study by^[15] All *Klebsiella* species isolates (10%) and most *Pantoea* species (93%) were positive for ESBL and carbapenemase. All isolates *Escherichia coli* and *Acinetobacter baumannii* She was positive for ESBL. A large number of Grampositive bacteria showed resistance to vancomycin; in another study by.^[24] The majority were strains CoNS Methicillin- resistant, half were resistant to aminoglycosides, and one-third were resistant to macrolides and lincosamides. Half of the GN bacilli were resistant to beta-lactams.

In our current study, there was a significant effect ($p = 0.047$) of the disease prevalence rate in government hospitals 60 (56.1%) higher than in private hospitals. In a study^[25] the prevalence of sepsis among neonates admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit of the respective public hospitals in Dhaka was 69.35%.

Routine empiric use of broad-spectrum antibiotic agents should only be considered among critically ill term neonates until culture results are available. Optional genetic testing is increasingly being considered before aminoglycoside use to reduce the prevalence of permanent hearing loss.^[26] Further studies are needed because this has not been evaluated in the neonatal setting. In low-resource settings, or when hospitalization is not possible,

intramuscular gentamicin and oral amoxicillin are recommended instead of intravenous medications.^[27]

CONCLUSIONS

Out of 200 newborns, 107 (53%) positive cases infected with the disease were isolated. Most of those infected with the disease were males (62.6%), the EOS was higher 74(69.2%) than LOS 33(30.8%). and there was a significant effect ($p=0.047$). The prevalence of the disease in government hospitals (56.1%) is higher than in private hospitals. The most common type of pathogen was (*Staph.spp*) at a rate of (49.5%), followed by bacteria (*Pseudomonas.aeruginosa*, *E.coli* and *Klebsiella.spp*) distributed respectively (15.9%, 10.3%, 9.3%). The prevalence of GP bacteria in government hospitals (65.96%) is higher than in private hospitals, with statistically significant differences ($p<0.005$). There was a statistically significant effect ($p<0.05$) on bacterial resistance (GP – GN) to both drugs (Gentamycin, Piperacillin, Amoxicillin, Augmentin and Cefepime).

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